

Thermodynamic Study of M^{2+} -Noradrenaline Systems in Aqueous Solutions

PURUSHOTTAM B. CHAKRAWARTI*, B. L. VIJAYVARGIYA and H. N. SHARMA

Chemical Laboratories, M. L. B. College, Bhopal

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The interaction of noradrenaline, [1-(3,4 dihydroxyphenyl)-2-amino ethanol], with M^{2+} has been studied potentiometrically and the stepwise and the overall thermodynamic constants have been worked out.

NORADRENALINE is a direct acting catecholamine like adrenaline. It elevates the blood pressure in hypertensive states resulting from trauma, hemorrhage, central vasomotor depression and acute myocardial infarction. For this function noradrenaline possesses a wider margin of safety between its pressor and toxic doses than does adrenaline.

Although noradrenaline complexes of many transition metals have been reported in the literature¹⁻⁷, the interaction of this drug with M^{2+} in solution has not been studied so far. In continuation of our attempt⁸ to study interaction of catecholamines with M^{2+} , we report here the results of our studies with noradrenaline.

Experimental

All the reagents employed were of high purity. The sample of noradrenaline was obtained from Fluka, Switzerland. The preparation and standardisation of the metal ion and ligand solutions and other experimental details are the same as reported earlier⁸.

Stoichiometry of the adducts formed was ascertained by potentiometric (pH) and conductometric titrations. Toshniwal conductivity bridge using dip-type conductivity cell (cell constant 0.42) was used for the conductometric studies, while 'Systronics' pH-meter, type 322, using the combined glass electrode and reading 0.025 pH units was used for the potentiometric study.

The stepwise and overall formation constants were calculated at three temperatures, 0, 25 and 37° and at a fixed ionic strength of 0.1 M with KCl. The experimental procedure consists in titration of the following thermostated mixtures of solutions with a 0.2 M alkali solution and recording the pH after each addition of 0.05 ml of the alkali:

- i. Mixture (A): 5 ml of 0.02 M HCl.
- ii. Mixture (B): Mixture (A) + 10 ml of 0.01 M noradrenaline solution.
- iii. Mixture (C): Mixture (B) + 5 ml of 0.002 M metal solution.

The ionic strength of the above solutions was maintained to 0.1 M by adding the required quantity of 1.0 M KCl solution, keeping the total volume at 50 ml with double distilled water.

The values of $\bar{n}H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL^- were calculated using the Irving-Rossotti equations¹⁰, and the values of the formation constants ($\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$) were directly obtained from the formation curves. The refined values for the same were computed by the best least square fits and are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF M^{2+} -NORADRENALINE COMPLEXES

	°	$\mu = 0.1M$ KCl		$\log \beta_2$
		$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	
Be(II)	0°	8.53	3.40	11.93
	25°	7.95	3.10	11.05
	37°	7.25	3.05	10.30
Mg(II)	0°	6.18	1.64	7.82
	25°	5.16	2.14	7.40
	37°	5.16	2.03	7.19
Ca(II)	0°	5.67	1.38	7.05
	25°	5.11	1.41	6.52
	37°	4.74	1.04	5.78
Sr(II)	0°	4.48	1.08	5.56
	25°	4.42	1.00	5.42
	37°	4.30	0.87	5.27
Ba(II)	0°	4.42	0.62	5.04
	25°	3.97	0.52	4.47
	37°	3.46	0.56	4.01

The thermodynamic parameters computed for the reactions studied were free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes and have been calculated using the isotherm, the isobar and the Gibbs-Helmholtz's equations respectively at 25 and 37° and ionic strength of 0.1 M with KCl (Table 2).

The metal adducts of the drug were isolated from the solution and their composition was ascertained by the methods described earlier⁸. The percentage of nitrogen was determined by the modified micro Kjeldahl method^{8b}, while the quantity of water associated with the complex from the difference in weight obtained on heating the complexes above 110°. The physical properties of

* To whom all correspondence is to be made: 90/24, T. T. Nagar, Bhopal-462 005.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF M²⁺-NORADRENALINE ADDUCTS

		Free energy change Kcal/g mole			Enthalpy change Kcal/g mole			Entropy change Cal/deg/mole		
		-ΔG ₁	-ΔG ₂	-ΔG ₁ (Overall)	-ΔH ₁	-ΔH ₂	-ΔH ₂ (Overall)	ΔS ₁	ΔS ₂	ΔS ₂ (Overall)
Be(II)	0°	10.26	5.28	15.46	—	—	—	—	—	—
	25°	10.41	5.66	15.79	8.64	2.72	11.12	5.9	14.9	20.8
	37°	9.85	5.03	15.79	13.18	2.80	15.90	-10.7	9.4	-1.4
Mg(II)	0°	6.50	3.23	9.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
	25°	6.62	3.28	9.47	5.21	2.68	7.89	4.7	2.0	6.72
	37°	6.60	2.86	9.46	5.76	5.97	11.70	2.7	-10.0	-7.3
Ca(II)	0°	6.10	2.76	8.86	—	—	—	—	—	—
	25°	6.00	2.81	8.81	6.85	2.23	9.05	-2.8	1.9	1.3
	37°	5.74	2.36	8.10	8.58	5.76	14.34	-9.1	-10.9	-21.9
Sr(II)	0°	5.30	2.01	7.31	—	—	—	—	—	—
	25°	5.30	2.06	7.36	4.62	1.50	6.12	2.2	0.9	3.1
	37°	4.94	2.04	7.98	-7.30	1.78	9.10	-7.7	0.8	-6.9
Ba(II)	0°	4.83	1.56	5.78	—	—	—	—	—	—
	25°	4.74	1.44	6.18	5.81	2.83	8.64	-3.6	-4.6	-17.0
	37°	4.43	1.43	5.86	7.74	2.51	10.25	-10.7	-3.5	-14.1

the compounds isolated and their analytical data are given in Table 3, along with the important ir frequencies (recorded on Perkin Elmer infrared spectrophotometer, model 237).

 TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL DATA AND IMPORTANT FREQUENCIES OF M²⁺ COMPLEXES OF NORADRENALINE

Compound	Props.	Metal %	N %	H ₂ O %	NH sec. bending	OH bending
Noradren.	—	—	—	—	1640 vs 1360 s 1610 vs 1085 s 830 w 1285 w 1360 s	1360 s 1075 s 1360 s
BeI ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dirty yellow*	2.4 (2.61)**	8.21 (8.12)	5.03 (5.2)	1640 w 1610 w	1360 s 1075 s
MgI ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow brown*	6.0 (6.06)	7.0 (7.07)	9.0 (9.09)	1640 w 1610 m 825 m	1360 s 1250 s 1050 w
CaI ₂ .2H ₂ O	Reddish brown*	9.6 (9.7)	6.6 (6.8)	8.2 (8.38)	1640 s 830 w	1390 s 1260 s 1080 m
SrI ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dark brown*	19.12 (19.1)	6.0 (6.1)	7.74 (7.7)	—	—
BaI ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dark brown*	26.87 (26.97)	5.54 (5.5)	7.0 (7.1)	1640 w 830 w	1360 w 1270 m 1080 vs

* Soluble in water and alcohol, hygroscopic and decomposes before melting.

** Values in the parenthesis are the Calcd. values.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric and potentiometric (pH) titrations clearly indicate formation of ML and ML₂ adducts between M²⁺ and adrenaline. The pH titrations show liberation of only one proton during chelation of each molecule of noradrenaline. Hence, the complexation of two molecules of the ligand with M²⁺ may be represented as follows :

where,

Formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) adducts was also confirmed by the values of $\bar{n}$, which were in no case greater than 1.8.

An analysis of the formation curves indicates that noradrenaline follows the same pattern of addition to metal as was found for adrenaline⁸ or as reported for aminoacids⁹. First, one atom of the metal combined with one molecule of noradrenaline. The 1 : 1 adduct thus formed did not appreciably combine with a second molecule of noradrenaline to give 1 : 2 complex until at least 80% of the 1 : 1 adduct had been formed. This indicates that the formation of the two species is independent of each other.

Complexation follows the standard pattern¹⁰. Comparison of stability constant data with corresponding adrenaline system suggests that stability of the noradrenaline systems is greater due to presence of primary amino group.

The analytical data for the isolated adducts gave the composition of these adducts to be ML₂.2H₂O, which is similar to that obtained for adrenaline adducts with these ions⁸. The ir frequencies of the isolated adducts indicate considerable change in the characteristic frequencies of phenolic -OH group in all the adducts, suggesting that the complexation might have taken place through the phenolic hydroxyl groups forming a five membered ring as suggested by Andrews *et al*¹. Further, the potentiometric (pH) titrations indicated liberation of only one proton during the complexation of each molecule of the ligand. Hence, considering the coordination number of the metal ions=6, the following general structure may be given for the ML₂ adduct in confirmation of the structure reported earlier⁸ :

The remaining two coordination positions are filled with two water molecules. This finds confirmation in the presence of the bands at frequencies 3600-3200 and 880-650 in ir spectra of these adducts (Table 3).

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